

Some Observations on the Luminescence of Benzimidazole and its Complexes with Cobalt(II)

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A new absorption band in the region 300-400 nm has been found in concentrated solutions of benzimidazole in DMSO. This has been interpreted as due to a dimeric association of benzimidazole. Concentrated solutions of benzimidazole also exhibit a fluorescence on excitation with near uv radiation at ambient temperature. Complexes of benzimidazole with divalent cobalt also exhibit a similar fluorescence.

IN view of their biological importance¹⁻⁴ the absorption and emission from substituted imidazoles have received considerable attention⁵. Although benzimidazole (HBZD) has been investigated⁶ we felt the need of reinvestigating the emission at higher concentrations specifically to investigate the role of association and complex formation on the luminescence. In the course of our studies a new absorption band could be detected in the region 300-400 nm with a concentrated solution of HBZD in DMSO. The object of the present investigation is to study the absorption and the corresponding emission in details.

Experimental

The fluorescence spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Fluorescence Spectrophotometer Model MPF 44A and in a set up described by Purkayastha and Basu⁷. The absorption spectra were recorded in a Beckman Spectrophotometer Model DU. The excited state lifetime measurements were made in a set up described by Chowdhury and others⁸ under excitation with 337 nm from a nitrogen laser.

Benzimidazole⁹ and its complexes¹⁰ were prepared by methods given in literature. Solvents were purified by standard methods^{11,12}. The purity of benzimidazole was established by its m.p., microanalysis and Tlc.

Results and Discussion

The low temperature (-180°) absorption spectra of benzimidazole (HBZD) consists of three principal bands⁹: 206 nm (1B_b), 251 nm (1L_a) and 279 nm (1L_b). Such bands are also present, a little shifted in position, in cyclohexane, at 20° . 1L_b band exhibits considerable vibrational structure. All these bands are $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions, $n-\pi^*$ bands could not be detected in either of the solvents. The following absorption bands have also been

reported¹³: 243, 272, 279 nm (neutral ethanol), 266, 274 nm (ethanol acidified with HCl), 241, 272, 278 nm (ethanol made alkaline with NaOH).

It has been observed by us that concentrated solutions of HBZD in DMSO exhibit a broad absorption band extending well upto 400 nm at laboratory temperature (Fig. 1). The detailed structure of the broad absorption band becomes more pronounced on using a more concentrated solution (Fig. 6). It has been found that Lambert

Fig. 1. Absorbance of 0.2 (M) HBZD in 5 cm cells.
(I) DMSO; (II) Ethanol; (III) Mixture of DMSO (24.5% v/v) and Benzene (74.5% v/v).

TABLE 1—FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF BENZIMIDAZOLE

Solvent	Concentration	Fluorescence Spectra			Excitation Spectra	
		Exciting Radiation (nm)	Fluorescence peaks (nm)		Wave length monitored (nm)	Observed peaks (nm)
DMSO	0.2047(M)	365	413	447	450	302 328 365 397
	0.2047(M)	400	460	480		
	0.20 (M)	365	412	430	470	302 320 368 405
	0.1023(M)					
	0.0512(M)					
0.01 (M)	365	412	433			
Ethanol	0.10 (M)	365	385	412 428		
Ethanol + Acetic acid [0.2(M) in acid]	0.10 (M)	365	385	412 443		
Ethanol + NaOH [0.2(M) in NaOH]	0.10 (M)	365	385	412		
Acetone	0.10 (M)	365	385	413 430		
	0.10 (M)	400	432	455		

Beer's Law is not obeyed at 328, 340, 365 nm over the concentration range 0.02M to 0.04M.

It is known that a structured fluorescence band centred around 283 nm is obtained⁶ on irradiating ethanolic solutions of HBZD at -180°. During the present investigations it has been found that concentrated solutions of HBZD in DMSO at room

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of HBZD in DMSO at concentrations (I) 0.2047(M), (II) 0.1023(M), (III) 0.0512(M), (IV) 0.010(M) with exciting radiation 365 nm; (V) fluorescence spectra of 0.2047(M) HBZD in DMSO with exciting wavelength 400 nm.

Fig. 3. Excitation spectra of HBZD in DMSO. (I) monitoring 450 nm, concn.=0.2047(M), (IIA) & (IIB) monitoring 470 nm, concn.=0.20(M).

temperature exhibit a new luminescence under excitation with 365 nm (Figs. 2 and 3) and Table 1. It has been found that emission peaks are not affected by bubbling a stream of nitrogen through DMSO solutions. Since absorption spectra is marginally affected by solvents and deoxygenation has no effect on the emission spectra it appears that the new absorption band is not due to a solute-solvent interaction and the emission spectra is not due to a solute - O₂ complex.

The excitation spectra monitoring 412, 440, 450 and 470 nm exhibit four distinct peaks at 302, 328, 365 nm and the fourth in the range 390-405 nm. Since the excitation spectra are similar it appears that the emission peaks at 412, 440, 450 and 470 nm are due to the same species. Since there is a correspondence with the absorption tail we may assign this as a emission corresponding to the 300-400 nm broad absorption.

From the decay curve of a concentrated solution (0.40M) in alcohol, under excitation with 337 nm from a nitrogen laser, a half life time of $\sim 4 \times 10^{-4}$ sec is obtained. In alcoholic solutions, the lifetime of the excited state, remains the same at room temperatures (30°) and at liquid nitrogen temperature. A similar value of the lifetime is obtained for a 0.20 (M) solution in DMSO at ambient temperatures. These lifetimes remain the same over the wave length range 400-470 nm. A previous estimate of phosphorescence lifetime under excitation with 1L_b is reported to be ~ 1 second¹⁴.

These observations may be best understood in terms of an association between two molecules of HBZD to form a dimer. This is consistent with the known behaviour of imidazoles to undergo intermolecular polymeric association¹⁵. The dimerisation may be represented as

where

a = stoichiometric concentration of HBZD,
x = equilibrium concentration of dimer.

If x^2 is small, the equation may be simplified to

$$\frac{a^2}{d} = \frac{2a}{\epsilon l} + \frac{1}{K \epsilon l} \quad \dots (2)$$

where d = measured absorbance.

The plot of $\frac{a^2}{d}$ vs 2a should give a straight line, from the slope and intercept of which, K can be calculated as

$$K = \frac{\text{slope}}{\text{intercept}}$$

The applicability of a similar equation to the formation constant of the complex $FeSCN^{2+}$ has been reported earlier¹⁵.

The plot of $\frac{a^2}{d}$ vs 2a for three different wave lengths in the concentration range 0.20-0.40 (M) using 5 cm cell, is given in Fig. 4. The slope and

Fig. 4. Association equilibrium of HBZD in DMSO.

intercepts obtained by a least square fit, gives the following values of K.

Wave length (nm)	K
328	8.94
340	5.68
365	1.54

The equilibrium constants are found to be low and dependent on wave length. Such a dependence of equilibrium constant on wave length has also been observed for charge transfer complexes^{16,17}.

Such an associative interaction could result in a considerable reordering of the energy levels of the monomer and it appears that the new absorption band of the dimer corresponds to the red shifted monomer band. The observed lifetime is considerably lower than that observed for phosphorescence and relatively higher than conventional fluorescence lifetimes, and is independent of temperature. Since the intensity of the absorption band is not enhanced in presence of KI, it appears that the emission is one of fluorescence. The relatively high lifetime might conceivably be due to the presence of a forbidden level in the dimer below an allowed one.

It has been reported⁶ that both fluorescence and phosphorescence of the benzimidazolium cation are observed at -180° under irradiation with 1L_b band and that the luminescence characteristics of the cation are similar to the free base. The effect of acid, base and solvent on fluorescence were therefore investigated.

It has been found that the fluorescence characteristics of HBZD is affected by the nature of the solvent media (Fig. 5). In acetone a new peak 385 nm is observed and the longer wave length fluorescence absorption becomes broad and diffuse. Fluorescence spectra in ethanol is also similar. Compared to DMSO, fluorescence intensities are much weaker in both these solvents. HBZD ($pK_a = 5.52$)¹⁸ as a base is comparable to pyridine ($pK_a = 5.23$)¹⁸. The proton attached to pyrrolic nitrogen in HBZD is capable of hydrogen bonding with acetone, and this seems to be the cause of the differences in fluorescence spectra of HBZD in DMSO and acetone.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence spectra with exciting radiation of 365 nm. (I) 0.10(M) HBZD in ethanol, (II) 0.010(M) HBZD in ethanol-acetic acid (0.20M); (III) 0.10(M) HBZD in ethanol-NaOH (0.20M); (IV) $[Co(HBZD)_2(NO_3)_2]$ in acetone; (V) 0.10(M) HBZD in acetone.

The fluorescence spectra of HBZD in acidified ethanol and in ethanol containing alkali is also very weak in intensity and is similar to that in ethanol. A diffuse and weak near uv absorption is also found for HBZD in DMSO containing NaOH and $HClO_4$ (Fig.6). It appears that the fluorescence and absorption of HBZD in acidic and alkaline medium is a characteristic of the resonance stabilised amidine group as shown in Fig. 7. With the idea that a metal ion may help to bring two HBZD molecules closer, we studied the luminescence and absorption characteristics of three complexes of divalent cobalt, $[Co(HBZD)_4](ClO_4)_2$, $[Co(HBZD)_2(NO_3)_2]$ and $[Co(BZD)_2]$. The absorption spectra of these complexes in the visible region are well known¹⁰. It has been observed that the uv absorption spectra

Fig. 6. Absorbance of HBZD in 1 cm cell. — 0.4(M) in DMSO; - - - 0.2(M) in DMSO perchloric acid (0.20M); - · - · 0.15(M) in DMSO-NaOH (0.20M); ···· Absorbance of 0.4(M) HBZD in DMSO in 5 cm cell.

in DMSO (Fig. 8) and the luminescence characteristics—in DMSO (Table 2) of these complexes are similar to that of the free ligand. As a representative example, the luminescence spectra of $[Co(HBZD)_2(NO_3)_2]$ is shown in Fig. 9 and the decay curve of this complex is given in Fig.10. Its excited state half lifetime is also same as that of the free ligand.

The long wave length fluorescence in acetone of two of these complexes shows loss of sharp contour (Fig.11). This can also be explained by the capability of these complexes to form hydrogen bonds with acetone. Pyrrolic proton is available for hydrogen bond formation for $[Co(HBZD)_2(NO_3)_2]$ and

TABLE 2—FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF Co(II) COMPLEXES OF BENZIMIDAZOLE

Compound	Saturated soln in	Fluorescence Spectra			Excitation Spectra		
		Exciting Radiation (nm)	Fluorescence peaks (nm)		Wave length monitored (nm)	Observed peaks (nm)	
[Co(HBZD) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	DMSO	365	412	420	428	430	323 363 381
	Acetone	400	455			455	323 368 398
[Co(BZD) ₂]	DMSO	365	390	413			
	Acetone	400	432	455			
[Co(HBZD) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	DMSO	365	405	425			
	Acetone	365	405	428			

Fig. 8. Absorbance of saturated solutions in DMSO in 5 cm cells of (I) [Co(HBZD)₄](ClO₄)₂, (II) [Co(HBZD)₂(NO₃)₂], (III) [Co(BZD)₂].

[Co(HBZD)₄](ClO₄)₂ since coordination occurs through lone pair of the pyridine nitrogen¹⁰. For [Co(BZD)₂], where bond formation takes place from a deprotonated pyrrolic nitrogen¹⁰, fluorescence spectra remains unaffected by acetone.

The observation that the absorption and fluorescence characteristics of the complexes in DMSO are similar only to concentrated solutions of HBZD in DMSO, lends further support to the presence of an associative interaction between molecules of the ligand in DMSO. Studies on mixed ligand complexes containing one molecule of HBZD could help towards a better understanding of the emission spectra.

Fig. 9. Fluorescence spectra of a saturated solution of [Co(HBZD)₂(NO₃)₂] in DMSO. (I) Exciting radiation 365 nm, (II) Exciting radiation 400 nm, (III) Excitation spectra monitoring 430 nm, (IV) Excitation spectra monitoring 455 nm.

Fig. 10. Decay curve of [Co(HBZD)₂(NO₃)₂] in DMSO. Time base = 0.2 milliseconds per division.

Fig. 11. Fluorescence spectra with exciting radiation of 365 nm.

- I, CO(BZD)₂ in DMSO ;
- - - II, CO(BZD)₂ in acetone ;
- · - · - III, [CO(HBZD)₂](ClO₄)₂ in DMSO ;
- IV, [CO(HBZD)₂](ClO₄)₂ in acetone.

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